

РОЗВИТОК ВИЩОЇ ШКОЛИ

UDC [811.111.378.091.33-027.22]:004.77

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WEB-QUESTS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDYING AND TEACHING AS A VALUABLE RESOURCE AND EFFECTIVE TOOL

Purpose. This paper is a study of innovative methods of learning and teaching English with the help of Internet resources and students motivation to seek the necessary information at homework. **Methodology.** The main principle of the Web-Quest as a type of English language teaching is to motivate students. For example, by participation in the Web-Quest students, who were unsure of their knowledge, become more confident. Having clear goals and objectives, using computer skills, motivated young people more actively acts as a confident user of English. **Findings.** According to the technology of We-Quests students were asked to create one or more projects directly related to the successful execution of the work. It is a significant result of all the hard work of students, and it is the subject of evaluation. Evaluation is an essential component of Web-Quest or any other project, and from this point of view, the criteria should be clear and accessible to students from the very beginning. These instructions can and should be changed in order to differentiate and provide an oral presentation and written work. **Originality.** Basically, Web-Quests are mini-projects in which a higher percentage of the material obtained from the Internet. They can be created by teachers or students, depending on the type of training work. The author detailed the increase of possibilities in the search of Internet projects with other creative types of student work. They may include: review of the literature, essay writing, discussion of read works and other. **Practical value.** The paper confirmed that the roles and tasks, reflecting the real world, invites to cooperate, stimulate and train the thinking process at a higher level. That is why the use of Web-Quests can improve the language skills of the educational process (reading for information extraction, detailed reading, negotiations, oral and written communication, and other).

Keywords: Web-Quest; Internet resources; information search; learners; foreign language studying; activity; motivation; assignment; knowledge and skills; foreign language teaching

Introduction

Web-Quests as a valuable resource and efficient tool in studying and teaching English is being widely used around the world since they were developed in 1995 by Dr. Bernie Dodge at San Diego State University with early input from SDSU/Pacific Bell Fellow Tom March, the Educational Technology staff at San Diego Unified School District working with classroom teachers. Since those days, their idea is that thousands of

teachers have embraced Web-Quests as a way to make good use of the internet while engaging their students in the kinds of thinking that the 21st century requires. The model has spread around the world.

According to the author's method, a Web-Quest is an oriented tool for students in the format in which most information that learners work with comes from the web. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. A Web-Quest traditionally has 6 parts: Introduction; Task; Process; Evaluation; Conclusion; Credits. Those parts can be differed in some cases, but this basic

РОЗВИТОК ВИЩОЇ ШКОЛИ

framework developed by Dodge and March is the basis for almost all of Web-Quests that have been created. [7, 8, 12, 13, 14]

The «*Web-Quest*» definition has been refined over the years, and adapted for various different disciplines. Philip Benz describes a Web-quest as *a constructivist approach to learning*, where with the proper guidance and «scaffolding» students can accomplish far more actual learning than in traditional transmission-of-knowledge situations. To his mind students not only gather information together, examine it carefully, compare and organize what they've found on the web, they orient their activities towards a specific goal they've been given, often associated with one or more roles modeled on adult professions [6].

Purpose

The research is guided to direct the reader, with little or no training or experience in this medium as a language learning tool to one particularly engaging and wide-ranging option available, using the Internet which is both learner-centered and teacher-active. An option potentially involves learners' in practice of all skills and systems in English, while at the same time promoting learner independence and collaboration. In language teaching circles, this is known as a Web-Quest.

Methodology

Since those beginning days, thousands of teachers have embraced Web-Quests as a way to make good use of the internet while engaging their students in the kinds of thinking that the 21st century requires. So there is a clearly defined structure for these activities which should only really be taken as a basic guideline and everybody should design his/her Web-quests to suit the needs and learning styles of his/her students [10, 11, 12]. There are usually from four to six main basic components of an average Web-Quest:

1. The Introduction stage is usually used to introduce the overall theme of the Web-quest. It includes giving background information on the topic and, in the language learning context, often presents basic vocabulary and concepts which learners will need to understand in order to fulfill the assignment involved. The instructor should set the stage for the activity, catch the learner's attention,

draw them into the quest and provide background information [6].

The Task section of the Web-quest explains clearly and precisely what the learners will have to do as they work their way through the Web-quest. The task should obviously be highly motivating and interesting for the students, and strongly connected with a real-life situation.[6,16,17] This often involves the learners in a particular amount of role-play within a given situation (e.g. they find the approximate fare of a ticket between two certain cities or towns; information about the types of restaurants, a school social organizer has to organize a trip for his class to an English-speaking country; a travel agent needs to organize a conference in London; he needs to know real data that helps him to figure out how things are (companies, bookings, prices, attractions, entertainment, Internet browsing and search skills and more are presented) in real life; learners choose the appropriate class of the airplane among different ones according to the services provided on board, exchange the information concerning the onboard services on a train which ones are desired, such as «catering», «type of sleeper» or various other requests that can be found in the online booking form etc. [15]). Besides it should be in place here to state what the students will be required to do, to avoid surprises down the road, to detail what products will be expected and the tools that are to be used to produce them. The point is the formal description of what the students will produce in the Web-Quest. The task should be meaningful and fun. Creating it is the most difficult and creative part of developing a Web-Quest [6].

The Process part of a Web-quest directs the learners through many activities and research tasks, using a lot of predefined resources. These resources are the best web-based, and are usually presented in a clickable form within the task document. In the case of a language-based Web-quest, the Process stage of the Web-quest may introduce (or reproduce) lexical areas or grammatical issues which are important to the Task. Besides it will usually have one (or sometimes several) 'materials' which the learners are supposed to present at the end. They will often be the basis of the Evaluation stage. In this part a step-by-step description, concise and clearly laid out should be given; links to Internet sites interwoven within the

РОЗВИТОК ВИЩОЇ ШКОЛИ

steps are to be provided. The students should accomplish the task. It is frequently profitable to reinforce the written process with some demonstrations [8, 9].

The Evaluation stage can involve learners in self-evaluation, comparing and contrasting what they have created with co-learners and giving feedback on what they feel they have known, achieved, etc. A great importance is the way in which the students' performance will be evaluated. The standards should be fair, clear, consistent, and specific to the tasks set [8]. It will also include a teacher's evaluation and good Web-quests will provide direction to the teacher for this particular part of the process, display a set of instruction to appreciate the final result as objectively as possible. It is necessary to leave little room for question in this section to contacts.

The Resources which the students should use are indicated in this portion of the Web-Quests. Providing this assistance the students should focus on the exercise in processing information rather than just locating it. Though the instructor may search for the online resources as a separate step, it is useful to incorporate resources as links within the process section where they will be needed rather than just including them as a long list elsewhere. Having off-line resources like visiting lecturers and sculptures one can contribute greatly to the interest of the students [9].

In the conclusion section summarizing the experience, the process reflection, higher level questions that may be researched at another time ought to be presented. The instructors are also supposed to give «food» for thought as to where they can use the information they have learned, etc. The co-developers of the concept of Dr. Bernie Dodge and Tom March give some very sound advice to test the given structure by own experience, define its weaknesses and advantages, check what makes things strong and comment on the results in class as it will take only 15 minutes due to the users of the Web-Quests [7, 8, 12, 13, 14].

Findings

Most members of the language teaching profession realize that their students' learning potential increases when attitudes to the Web-Quests are positive and motivation to do it runs high. They think of incorporating the Web-Quests lesson for-

mat into language teaching and some activities in the form of a single organizing framework that English as foreign language (EFL) lecturers can use to integrate the projects method into language learning in the classroom and outside it giving more autonomy to students. English instructors cannot deny or ignore the significance of the Web-Quests in the process of teaching and learning. In the experience, there never seems to be enough time to cover all the language work that is necessary or obligatory within course contact hours [4]. That's why one of the most challenging aspects in foreign language teaching/learning is an individual self-independent assignment. So any task or activity that encourages contemporary students to continue working on their English outside the classroom is to be welcomed. It goes without saying that learning is more effective when learners are active in their learning process, assuming responsibility for their learning and participating in decisions which affect it [2]. A teacher's aim is to focus more on creating challenging and meaningful activities for students in the classroom and outside the classroom. And correction of home assignment should be learning-centered rather than teaching-centered. It should focus on motivating students to develop their own strategies for learning through home assignment [4].

Originality and practical value

The teacher maintains an essential role in this process as not only the one who would normally select or set up the Web-Quest, but who also plays an important role as a facilitator – providing support, «feeding» in language, monitoring and eventually, taking on a role in an evaluating capacity. It is important to give the correct amount of importance to a sensitive balance between helping students make their way through the Web-Quest, and disturbing their autonomy. Such autonomy is likely to boost learners' self-confidence and motivation. As much of the Web-Quest work takes place on the Internet, the teacher must ensure that all participants are sufficiently versed in basic navigation skills. This might even provide an opportunity for student teaching, as there will surely be some in groups who can give this kind of information and design some easy practice activities.

Web-Quests are motivating, funny, they reflect real-world roles and tasks, invite collaboration,

РОЗВИТОК ВИЩОЇ ШКОЛИ

promote and exercise «higher-level» thinking process and practice skills inherent to any language learning project, such as overall reading and detailed reading, negotiating ideas through spoken and written communication. Web-Quests incorporate listening skills, peers teaching and interaction. Students are involved in creating and producing their own ideas, with peers' and teachers' support, they do not only receive valuable feedback from their teacher, but are involved in reflecting on their work and engage in self-evaluation as well.

Conclusions

To work with Web-quests, an instructor should find well-chosen and motivating topics, coupled with up-to-date websites and he/she should access the wealth of the material on the Internet and besides pays attention both to the content and the language.

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ВЕБ-КВЕСТ ЯК ЦІННИЙ РЕСУРС ТА ЕФЕКТИВНИЙ ІНСТРУМЕНТ У ВИВЧЕННІ ТА ВИКЛАДАННІ АНГЛІЙСЬКОЇ МОВИ

Мета. Дана робота – дослідження інноваційної методики вивчення та викладання англійської мови за допомогою Інтернет-ресурсів і мотивації студентів до пошуку необхідної інформації під час виконання домашнього завдання. **Методика.** Головний принцип веб-квесту як типу викладання англійської мови полягає в умотивуванні студентів. Наприклад, завдяки участі у веб-квесті студенти, що мали сумніви стосовно своїх знань, стають більш впевненішими. Маючи чіткі цілі та завдання, використовуючи комп'ютерні навички, умотивована молодь більш активно виступає як впевнений користувач англійської мови. **Результати.** Згідно з технологією веб-квестів студентам було запропоновано створити один або більше проєктів, які безпосередньо пов'язані з успішним виконанням завдання. Це помітний результат всієї їхньої кропіткої роботи, і він повинен оцінюватися. Оцінювання – значна складова частина веб-квесту або будь-якого іншого проєкту, і з цієї точки зору критерії оцінювання повинні бути чіткими та доступними для студентів із самого початку. Ці вказівки можуть і повинні мінятися для того, щоб відрізнитися для усної презентації та письмової роботи. **Наукова новизна.** В основному, веб-квести – це міні-проєкти, в яких великий процент матеріалу постачається з Інтернету. Вони можуть створюватися викладачами або студентами, залежно від виду навчальної роботи. Автором деталізовано збільшення можливостей у процесах пошуку Інтернет-проєктів за допомогою інших творчих видів студентських робіт. Внесок автора – підсилення та збільшення пошуку Інтернет-проєктів за допомогою інших творчих видів студентських робіт. Ними можуть бути: аналіз літератури, написання творів, обговорення прочитаних джерел тощо. **Практична значимість.** У роботі підтверджено, що ролі та завдання, які відображають реальний світ, запрошують до співробітництва, активізують і тренують процес мислення на більш високому рівні. Саме тому застосування веб-квестів може покращувати практичні навички мови навчального процесу (читання для вилучення інформації, детальне читання, ведення переговорів, усна та письмова комунікація тощо).

Ключові слова: веб-квест; Інтернет-ресурси; пошук інформації; вивчення іноземної мови; навчання; мотивація; завдання; знання та вміння; викладання іноземної мови

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ВЕБ-КВЕСТ – ЦЕННЫЙ РЕСУРС И ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЙ ИНСТРУМЕНТ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ И ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Цель. Данная работа – исследование инновационной методики изучения и преподавания английского языка при помощи Интернет-ресурсов и мотивации студентов к поиску необходимой информации во время выполнения домашнего задания. **Методика.** Главный принцип веб-квеста как типа преподавания английского языка заключается в мотивации студентов. Например, благодаря участию в веб-квесте студенты, имеющие сомнения относительно своих знаний, становятся более уверенными. Имея четкие цели и задания, используя компьютерные навыки, мотивированная молодежь более активно выступает как уверенный пользователь английского языка. **Результаты.** Согласно технологии веб-квестов студентам было предложено создать один или больше проєктов, непосредственно связанных с успешным выполнением задания. Это заметный результат всей усердной работы студентов, и он является предметом оценивания. Оценивание – существенная составная веб-квеста или любого другого проєкта, и с этой точки зрения критерии должны быть ясными и доступными студентам с самого начала. Эти указания могут и должны быть изменены для того,

РОЗВИТОК ВИЩОЇ ШКОЛИ

чтобы различать и обеспечивать устную презентацию и письменную работу. **Научная новизна.** В основном, веб-квесты – это мини проекты, в которых больший процент материала получен из Интернета. Они могут быть созданы преподавателями или студентами, в зависимости от вида обучающей работы. Автором детализировано увеличение возможностей в процессах поиска Интернет-проектов при помощи других творческих видов студенческих работ. Ими могут быть: анализ литературы, написания сочинений, обсуждение прочитанных произведений и т.д. **Практическая значимость.** В работе подтверждено, что роли и задания, отображающие реальный мир, приглашают к сотрудничеству, активизируют и тренируют мыслительный процесс на более высоком уровне. Именно поэтому использование веб-квестов может улучшить практические навыки языка учебного процесса (чтение для извлечения информации, подробное чтение, ведение переговоров, устная и письменная коммуникация и др.).

Ключевые слова: веб-квест; Интернет-ресурсы; поиск информации; изучение иностранного языка; мотивация; задание; знания и умения; преподавание иностранного языка

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Prof. T. I. Vlasova, Dr. Phil. (Ukraine); Prof. O. I. Panchenko. Dr. Philol. (Ukraine) recommended this article to be published

Received: Jan. 20, 2015

Accepted: May 16, 2015